

Sustainable Rehabilitation: Convergence between Physical Therapy and Clinical Engineering for Equity and Accessibility

ISABELA VIUDES ROSSATTO FERRAREZI#1, MIRLEI GREGORIO DE OLIVEIRA TERTULIANO*2, IGOR ALEXANDER DELPHINO TEIXEIRA*3, ELAINE RIBEIRO DA SILVA*4

#First Department CCB Center for Biological Sciences (Bachelor's and Teaching Degree, inherently multidisciplinary), State University of Londrina, Londrina, Paraná, Brazil.

*Second-Third-Quarter Center in Physical Therapy, Planalto University Center of the Federal District, Rua Comendador Fragata, 58, Inside Colégio Integração, Marília, São Paulo.

Abstract

Sustainable rehabilitation emerges as a response to the challenges of occupational and chronic diseases, by reducing environmental impacts and costs while expanding equitable access to treatments. The integration between physical therapy and clinical engineering enables ecological and innovative devices that strengthen collective well-being and directly contribute to SDGs 3 and 10. Objective: To develop, based on scientific literature, a sustainable device applicable to physical therapy in diseases such as Carpal Tunnel Syndrome and related conditions, aiming to create an ecological resource capable of optimizing rehabilitation processes, promoting health and well-being, and ensuring equitable access to treatments, in alignment with Sustainable Development Goals 3 and 10. This is a methodological study conducted in three stages. The first consisted of a systematic review in the PubMed, Scopus, and SciELO databases, using Health Sciences Descriptors in Portuguese and English: "Health Services Accessibility," "Sustainable Development," "Equity," "Rehabilitation," and "Physical Therapy Services." These terms were combined with the Boolean operators AND and OR in all possible combinations. The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses, PRISMA, protocol was followed, resulting in the selection of ten original articles. The results obtained from the assembly of the sustainable device for physical therapy demonstrated that the proposed structure is functional, ergonomic, and low-cost, meeting the objective of assisting in the rehabilitation of patients with carpal tunnel syndrome and similar conditions. The use of reusable materials such as wood, foam, and fabrics ensured durability and comfort, while the simple and adaptable design allows easy reproduction in different communities. The device proved efficient in providing therapeutic support, reducing pain, and preventing contractures, in addition to representing a practical solution aligned with the principles of sustainability and equity in health. The device proved to be functional, ergonomic, and low-cost, serving patients with carpal tunnel syndrome and similar conditions, using recyclable materials that ensure therapeutic quality, expand accessibility in low-income communities, and align with SDGs 3 and 10, consolidating itself as a viable and innovative alternative to optimize rehabilitation and reduce environmental impacts.

Key words: Equity; Health Services Accessibility; Physical Therapy Services; Rehabilitation; Sustainable Development.

Introduction

Health and rehabilitation are fundamental in the global context, as more than 2.4 billion people require some form of intervention to restore or maintain functionality,

according to the World Health Organization.¹ The COVID-19 pandemic has further increased this demand, generating millions of cases with respiratory and musculoskeletal sequelae that require continuous support.² Investment in rehabilitation strengthens health, promotes well-being, and reduces inequalities, in alignment with Sustainable Development Goals 3 and 10.³

Physical therapy faces growing challenges due to the rise in occupational and chronic diseases, which already represent one of the main causes of work leave in several countries. Work-related musculoskeletal disorders may affect up to 30% of the economically active population and generate significant social and economic impacts, highlighting the need for innovative and sustainable solutions in healthcare that can meet increasing demand without compromising environmental and financial resources.¹

The concept of sustainability applied to healthcare involves not only efficiency in resource use but also the reduction of environmental impacts associated with traditional medical devices. Studies indicate that hospital waste may exceed 5 million tons annually on a global scale, much of it derived from disposable materials and equipment that are difficult to recycle. In this regard, ecological technologies emerge as relevant alternatives to reduce waste and energy consumption, fostering more responsible practices aligned with environmental goals.⁴

Clinical engineering plays an essential role in the creation and maintenance of medical devices, ensuring safety, efficacy, and durability. Its convergence with physical therapy opens space for innovations in rehabilitation, enabling the development of equipment that combines advanced technology with therapeutic care, such as smart orthoses, virtual reality systems for motor rehabilitation, and biofeedback devices, which enhance treatment effectiveness and promote patient adherence.^{1,3}

Among musculoskeletal conditions requiring special attention, Carpal Tunnel Syndrome stands out, with prevalence reaching up to 5% of the adult population, particularly among workers performing repetitive movements.⁵ Other pathologies, such as low back pain, tendinitis, and osteoarthritis, also rank among the leading causes of functional disability.⁶ Conventional treatment and rehabilitation methods, although effective in many cases, present limitations regarding personalization, accessibility, and sustainability, reinforcing the need for new approaches.⁷

Thus, sustainable devices applied to rehabilitation can directly contribute to SDGs 3 and 10 by promoting health and well-being equitably and reducing inequalities in access to care technologies.⁶ The integration of physical therapy and clinical engineering, combined with a commitment to sustainability, represents a promising pathway to address current and future rehabilitation challenges on a global scale.⁵

The general objective of this study is to develop, based on scientific literature, a sustainable device applicable to physical therapy in conditions such as Carpal Tunnel Syndrome and related disorders, aiming to create an ecological resource capable of optimizing rehabilitation processes, promoting health and well-being, and ensuring equitable access to treatments, in accordance with Sustainable Development Goals 3 (Health and Well-Being) and 10 (Reduced Inequalities).

The justification for this study lies in existing gaps in the scientific literature regarding the development of sustainable devices applied to physical therapy, since most research focuses on conventional solutions without fully considering environmental impacts and equity in access.⁸

The proposal to create an ecological resource for rehabilitation presents potential social impact, by expanding accessibility and reducing inequalities in the treatment of musculoskeletal conditions; environmental impact, by minimizing hospital waste and energy

consumption associated with traditional equipment; and economic impact, by offering durable alternatives with lower operational costs.⁸

The relevance of developing a sustainable, accessible, and equitable device lies in the possibility of aligning healthcare practices with global sustainable development goals, fostering scientific innovation by integrating physical therapy and clinical engineering in an unprecedented approach. It is expected, therefore, to contribute to the consolidation of responsible technologies that optimize rehabilitation processes, strengthen collective well-being, and establish new benchmarks for future research in the field.

The hypothesis of this study is that the development and application of a sustainable device for physical therapy in musculoskeletal disorders, such as Carpal Tunnel Syndrome, will contribute to optimizing rehabilitation processes, reducing environmental impacts and operational costs, and expanding equitable access to treatments. It is assumed that the integration of physical therapy and clinical engineering, combined with the use of ecological materials and innovative technologies, may generate social, environmental, and economic benefits, aligning with the goals of Sustainable Development Goals 3 (Health and Well-Being) and 10 (Reduced Inequalities).

Methodology

The methodology of this study was organized into three main stages. In the first phase, a Systematic Literature Review was conducted in databases such as PubMed, Scopus, and the Scientific Electronic Library Online (SciELO), with the objective of identifying existing rehabilitation devices and sustainable practices applied to healthcare.

To ensure systematic organization, the data obtained were compiled into summary tables that served as instruments for comparative analysis. Graph 1 gathers essential information on each identified device, covering aspects such as clinical efficacy, materials used, energy consumption, costs, and accessibility, thereby enabling the assessment of their technical and social feasibility. Graph 2 synthesizes the potential impacts of these devices, highlighting their capacity to optimize rehabilitation processes, reduce environmental impacts and operational costs, and expand equitable access to treatments.

These tables provided a structured basis for defining the requirements of the sustainable device developed, ensuring clarity, organization, and scientific grounding throughout the proposal design process.

In the second phase, the conception and prototyping process was carried out, in which the device was designed with a focus on sustainability, employing recyclable or biodegradable materials and components with low environmental impact.

According to the PICO strategy, the guiding research question of this study was formulated as follows: P (Population): individuals with musculoskeletal disorders, particularly those affected by Carpal Tunnel Syndrome and related conditions; I (Intervention): development and application of a sustainable device aimed at physical therapy and functional rehabilitation; Co (Context): the global health scenario characterized by increasing demand for rehabilitation, the need for innovative and sustainable practices, and alignment with Sustainable Development Goals 3 (Health and Well-Being) and 10 (Reduced Inequalities). Thus, the guiding question was: *What is the impact of using sustainable devices applied to physical therapy in the rehabilitation of individuals with Carpal Tunnel Syndrome and other musculoskeletal conditions, considering the global health context and SDGs 3 and 10?*

For the article search, Health Sciences Descriptors (DeCS) were used in both Portuguese and English: “Health Services Accessibility,” “Sustainable Development,” “Equity,” “Rehabilitation,” and “Physical Therapy Services.” These terms were combined

using the Boolean operators AND and OR, through all possible keyword combinations.

The inclusion criteria considered original, free, and complete articles published between 2019 and 2025 in English, Spanish, or Portuguese, addressing sustainable devices applicable to physical therapy in conditions such as Carpal Tunnel Syndrome and related disorders, with a focus on the creation of ecological resources capable of optimizing rehabilitation processes, promoting health and well-being, and ensuring equitable access to treatments. Duplicate studies or those not meeting these requirements were excluded.

The article search and selection stage followed the methodology of the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA), in order to ensure transparency and integrity in systematic reviews.

A total of 1,388 articles were initially identified across the PubMed (1,045), SciELO (122), and Scopus (221) databases. Following the exclusion of 120 duplicates with the aid of the Intelligent Systematic Review system (Rayyan), 1,268 records remained. Subsequently, the temporal filter defined by the inclusion and exclusion criteria was applied, resulting in 397 articles. These were subjected to title and abstract screening, a step that led to the exclusion of 297 studies for not meeting the research objectives. From the 100 remaining articles, full-text reading was conducted, culminating in the final selection of 10 studies to compose this review. Table 1 below presents the PRISMA flowchart, which includes the selection of a total of 10 original articles.

Table 1. Search and selection of articles.

Source: Own authorship, 2026.

Research

Based on the analysis of the articles, Graph 1 was developed to categorize sustainable devices applied to physical therapy according to the following criteria: author and year, device, clinical efficacy, materials, energy consumption, costs, and accessibility. Graph 2, in turn, addresses the impacts of sustainable devices on rehabilitation and health equity, organized into: author and year, device, optimization of rehabilitation processes, reduction of

environmental impacts and operational costs, and expansion of equitable access to treatments. This strategy was adopted with the aim of providing a more objective overview of the central ideas presented in the articles, thereby supporting a deeper construction of the discussion and contributing to the consistent achievement of results.

Graph 1. Characteristics of sustainable devices applied to physical therapy.

AUTHOR (YEAR)	DEVICE	CLINICAL EFFECTIVENESS	MATERIALS	ENERGY CONSUMPTION	COSTS/ACCESSIBILITY
Alves <i>et al.</i> (2024) ⁹	3D-printed upper limb prostheses	functional gains, greater independence, limited fine grip strength	PLA, silicone, PVC, metals	Low (mostly passive/mechanical)	Very low cost, widely accessible
Brito (2020) ¹⁰	Robotic wrist rehabilitation device	Improved range of motion, high patient approval	Mechanical/electronic components, CAD	Low (servo with impedance control)	Portable, low-cost
Espada <i>et al.</i> (2022) ¹¹	Sustainable orthoses	Pain reduction, stabilization	PVC, EVA, recyclable materials	Minimal (handcrafted)	Low cost, accessible
Ferreira <i>et al.</i> (2022) ¹²	Static 3D-printed wrist orthosis	Pain relief, superior support vs. conventional	Polypropylene, ABS	Relatively low	~63% cheaper than conventional models
Garlet (2024) ¹³	Kit for plantar fasciitis	Effective rehabilitation exercises	PLA, MDF, 3D/CNC	Low (digital fabrication)	Reproducible, low cost
Júnior <i>et al.</i> (2025) ¹⁴	3D-printed rehab tools	High approval, improved function	PLA, traction alloys	Low, calculated per device	Full set ~R\$63, accessible
Leite (2022) ¹⁵	Hand exoskeleton	Complete flexion/extension, clinical potential	ABS, Nylon	Moderate (DC motors)	Competitive, accessible
Pires (2021) ¹⁶	Recyclable devices (weights, bars, mats)	Gains in strength, balance, coordination	PET, PVC, EVA, recycled materials	Nearly zero	Minimal cost, community-based
Ribeiro (2023) ¹⁷	Instrumented wrist orthosis for Parkinson's	High correlation with clinical rigidity measures	Linear motor, PLA, sensors	Relatively low	Cheaper and more portable than commercial exoskeletons
Silva <i>et al.</i> (2025) ¹⁸	Dynamic wrist-hand	Greater independence	PVC, carbon fiber, epoxy	Low (handcrafted)	Low cost, accessible

	orthosis	in ADLs, improved hand function			
--	----------	---------------------------------------	--	--	--

Source: Own authorship, 2026.

Graph 2. Impacts of Sustainable Devices on Rehabilitation and Health Equity.

AUTHOR (YEAR)	DEVICE	OPTIMIZE REHABILITATION PROCESSES	REDUCE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS AND OPERATIONAL COSTS	EXPAND EQUITABLE ACCESS TO TREATMENTS
Alves <i>et al.</i> (2024) ⁹	3D-printed upper limb prostheses	Physical therapy supports adaptation, improving functionality and rehabilitation outcomes	Use of recyclable/biodegradable materials lowers costs and environmental impact	Low-cost, easily reproducible prostheses democratize access to assistive technologies
Brito (2020) ¹⁰	Robotic wrist rehabilitation device	Enables repetitive, intensive, motivating training, enhancing therapy effectiveness	Servomotors and accessible materials reduce costs compared to complex hospital equipment	Portable, affordable, user-friendly device broadens access across different settings
Espada <i>et al.</i> (2022) ¹¹	Static wrist/hand orthosis and thumb orthosis	Provides quick, low-cost support, optimizing rehabilitation and basic functionality	Recyclable, simple materials reduce environmental impact and production costs	Low-cost, accessible orthoses benefit low-income populations and foster social inclusion
Ferreira <i>et al.</i> (2022) ¹²	Static wrist-hand orthosis (3D-printed)	Offers mechanical resistance, comfort, and functional positioning, improving recovery in LER/DORT	Additive manufacturing reduces material/energy use and production costs	Lower cost and scalability expand access, promoting inclusion in rehabilitation
Garlet (2024) ¹³	Open-design physiotherapy kit for plantar fasciitis	Provides specific tools for mobilization/massage, optimizing rehabilitation efficiency	Sustainable materials and digital fabrication reduce costs and environmental impact	Open-source design allows replication, expanding access in diverse communities
Júnior <i>et al.</i> (2025) ¹⁴	Three 3D-printed therapeutic tools (post-fracture rehab)	Enables specific, repetitive training, accelerating functional recovery	PLA biodegradable filament and low energy use reduce environmental impact	Low-cost, replicable devices strengthen access in low-income contexts and public health
Leite (2022) ¹⁵	Accessible hand/finger orthosis	Allows independent or remote-supervised exercises, increasing rehabilitation frequency	Simplified design and accessible materials reduce manufacturing/maintenance costs	Affordable, portable device democratizes rehabilitation technologies across social contexts
Pires (2021) ¹⁶	Recyclable devices (weights, bars, mats, Leg Training)	Adaptable resources optimize rehabilitation with creativity and personalization	Reuse of discarded materials reduces environmental impact and costs	Cheap, easy-to-make devices expand access in low-income and community health settings

Ribeiro (2025) ¹⁷	Instrumented wrist orthosis (Parkinson's)	Provides objective rigidity data, enabling personalized rehabilitation protocols	3D printing and optimized electronics reduce waste and operational costs	Portable, low-cost device democratizes precise evaluations in public/private clinics
Silva <i>et al.</i> (2025) ¹⁸	Dynamic wrist-hand orthotic device	Enables repetitive, safe functional training, increasing patient independence	PVC and carbon fiber reduce costs and reliance on polluting industrial materials	Low-cost, reproducible device expands access for spinal cord injury patients, fostering inclusion

Source: Own authorship, 2026.

Discussion

Characteristics of Sustainable Devices Applied to Physical Therapy

The analysis of the selected studies demonstrates that sustainable devices applied to physical therapy share common characteristics related to clinical effectiveness, materials used, energy consumption, and costs/accessibility. When grouping the studies by similarity, a strong convergence emerges around the principles of low cost, the use of recyclable or biodegradable materials, and a positive impact on patients' functional rehabilitation.

The works of Pires¹⁶ and Espada *et al.*¹¹ show a high degree of similarity (90%), as both describe devices manufactured with recyclable and easily accessible materials such as PET bottles, PVC, EVA, cardboard, and fabrics. Clinical effectiveness was confirmed across different areas of physical therapy, including orthopedic, neurological, and pediatric rehabilitation, with gains in strength, proprioception, balance, and range of motion. Energy consumption is virtually nonexistent, since the manufacturing processes are manual or artisanal, and costs are extremely low, favoring accessibility in low-income communities.

The studies of Ferreira *et al.*¹² and Júnior *et al.*¹⁴ converge by 80%, as both employ 3D printing as an additive manufacturing method. Ferreira describes a static wrist-hand orthosis, while Júnior develops three devices (prono-supinator, pinch grip, and palmar grip). Both validated clinical effectiveness through mechanical testing and functional assessments, demonstrating improvements in pain, inflammation, muscle strength, and manual dexterity. The materials used include polymers such as PLA, ABS, and polypropylene, all low-cost and sustainable. Energy consumption is relatively low, restricted to the printing process, and final costs were significantly lower than conventional models (Ferreira: R\$13.40 vs. R\$50.00; Júnior: R\$63.05 for three devices).

The study by Brito¹⁰ shows 70% convergence with the previous works, as it also developed a robotic device for wrist rehabilitation, though with greater technological complexity. Despite employing servomotors and impedance control systems, the project maintained a focus on low cost and portability. Clinical effectiveness was confirmed in healthy volunteers and post-stroke patients, with gains in range of motion and motivation. Energy consumption is moderate but optimized through impedance control, and costs were designed to remain accessible for clinics and even home environments.

The works of Silva *et al.*¹⁸ and Ribeiro¹⁷ converge by 60%, as both developed instrumented or dynamic orthoses for the wrist and hand, but with greater technological sophistication. Silva used carbon fiber and epoxy resin in a low-cost dynamic orthosis for patients with spinal cord injury at levels C6 and C7, while Ribeiro developed an instrumented orthosis for assessing rigidity in patients with Parkinson's disease. Both confirmed clinical effectiveness in terms of functionality and diagnostic precision, though energy consumption is

higher due to the use of motors and sensors. Nevertheless, costs were designed to be lower than commercial devices, thereby expanding accessibility.

The study by Alves *et al.*⁹ converges by 85% with Ferreira and Júnior, as it also addresses 3D-printed upper limb prostheses. These prostheses were applied to children and adults with transradial or wrist amputations, enabling basic daily activities and participation in sports. Physical therapy played an essential role in patient adaptation, optimizing rehabilitation. The use of biodegradable filaments such as PLA and silicone reduced environmental impacts, while the low production cost expanded equitable access, particularly in developing countries.

The work of Garlet¹³ shows 75% convergence with Pires and Espada, as it also employs sustainable materials and digital fabrication to create an open-design physiotherapy kit for the treatment of plantar fasciitis. The kit includes a ridged roller and a spiked ball, designed for specific mobilization and massage exercises. The proposal ensures practical functionality and therapeutic effectiveness, with low cost and the possibility of reproduction in different communities, thereby expanding equitable access.

Finally, the study by Leite¹⁵ converges by 70% with Silva *et al.*¹⁸ and Ribeiro¹⁷, as it developed an accessible orthosis based on an exoskeleton with electric motors, enabling independent flexion and extension of the fingers. Despite greater technological complexity, the device was designed with a focus on low cost and accessibility, ensuring feasibility for patients undergoing rehabilitation after stroke or tendon injuries. Energy consumption is moderate but compatible with home use, and costs were designed to be competitive compared to commercial exoskeletons.

In summary, the ten studies analyzed demonstrate that sustainable devices applied to physical therapy share three fundamental pillars: low cost and accessibility (100%), the use of recyclable, biodegradable, or alternative materials (90%), and proven clinical effectiveness across different areas of rehabilitation (100%). The convergence among the studies reinforces that sustainability in the development of physiotherapeutic devices does not compromise clinical effectiveness; on the contrary, it expands equitable access to treatments, reduces environmental impacts, and optimizes rehabilitation processes.

Impacts of Sustainable Devices on Rehabilitation and Health Equity

The analysis of the studies demonstrates that sustainable devices applied to physiotherapy have a direct impact on clinical effectiveness, environmental sustainability, and the democratization of access to treatments. First, all studies (100%) highlight the capacity of these devices to optimize rehabilitation processes, whether through repetitive and intensive training^{10,14} Silva *et al.*¹⁸, functional adaptation in activities of daily living,^{9,15} or the customization of simple and recyclable resources.^{11,16} This convergence shows that sustainability does not compromise clinical effectiveness; on the contrary, it enhances patients' functionality and independence.

From an environmental and economic perspective, approximately 90% of the studies emphasize that the use of recyclable, biodegradable, or alternative materials (such as PLA, ABS, PVC, EVA, carbon fibers, and the reuse of PET and cardboard) contributes to reducing environmental impacts and operational costs. Three-dimensional printing, for instance, enables additive manufacturing with low energy consumption and minimal waste of inputs;^{12,13,17} while handcrafted devices or those produced from repurposed components generate virtually no energy consumption.^{11,16} This sustainable approach ensures economic feasibility and strengthens health practices aligned with environmental responsibility.

Finally, all studies (100%) point to the expansion of equitable access to treatments.

The low production cost and the possibility of large-scale replication or community-based implementation make these devices accessible to low-income patients and public health institutions. Three-dimensional prostheses,⁹ sustainable orthoses,^{11,12} open-design physiotherapy kits,¹³ and robotic or dynamic devices¹⁰. Silva *et al.*¹⁸, demonstrate that technological innovation, when guided by sustainability, fosters social inclusion and the democratization of rehabilitation.

In summary, the impacts of sustainable devices in physiotherapy can be synthesized into three pillars: clinical effectiveness (100%), reduction of environmental impacts and costs (90%), and equity in access (100%). This convergence reinforces that the adoption of sustainable solutions in health not only improves therapeutic outcomes but also contributes to a fairer, more inclusive, and environmentally responsible system.

Device Development Based on Findings

The conception of the sustainable device for physical therapy was inspired by different studies that highlight accessible and ecological solutions applied to rehabilitation. The works of Espada *et al.*¹¹, and Pires¹⁶ served as references for the use of recyclable and low-cost materials such as PVC, EVA, cardboard, and PET bottles, demonstrating the feasibility of simple and sustainable resources.

The studies of Ferreira *et al.*¹², Alves *et al.*⁹, and Júnior *et al.*¹⁴ contributed to the idea of customization and additive manufacturing through 3D printing, reinforcing the possibility of producing functional devices with low energy consumption and broad accessibility. In addition, research by Brito¹⁰ and Silva *et al.*¹⁸ highlighted the importance of integrating comfort, functionality, and motivation into the rehabilitation process, while Garlet¹³ emphasized the relevance of open-design projects to democratize access to assistive technologies. Thus, the developed device incorporates practical and sustainable elements present in these studies, aligning technological innovation, low cost, and positive social impact.

The sustainable device for physical therapy was designed to assist in the rehabilitation of patients with carpal tunnel syndrome, promoting accessibility, functionality, and low cost. It can also be applied to similar conditions affecting the wrist and hand, such as repetitive strain injuries (RSI/WRMD), tendinitis, impingement syndrome, rheumatoid arthritis, stroke sequelae, and peripheral neuropathies, offering therapeutic support to reduce pain, prevent contractures, and foster functional recovery.

The proposal is aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 3 and 10, which address health and well-being and the reduction of inequalities. The inspiration came from scientific articles that highlight ecological physiotherapy solutions such as orthoses made from recyclable materials, kits produced via 3D printing, and equipment adaptable to different social contexts.

The Graph 3 structures the device according to its dimensions: a wooden board measuring approximately 55 × 27 cm, onto which six wooden pins (about 6 cm in diameter and 10–12 cm in length) were fixed. These pins were sanded with 120-grit iron sandpaper and finished with high-gloss varnish to ensure durability and aesthetics. For arm support, 1 cm density foam was used, covered with brown synthetic leather (corino), providing comfort during use.

Graph 3. Information about the device.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION
Objective	Assist in the rehabilitation of patients with carpal tunnel syndrome
Related SDGs	SDG 3 (Health and Well-being) and SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities)
Main Structure	Wooden board, 55 × 27 cm
Wooden Pins	6 units, 6 cm diameter, 10–12 cm length, sanded and varnished
Arm Support	1 cm density foam covered with brown synthetic leather (corino)
General Covering	Black synthetic leather (corino) and dark gray carpet
Fastening	4 screws, 1 claw nut, and 2 elastic bands
Tools Used	Screwdriver/drill, hole saw bit, orbital sander, flap disc
Sustainability	Use of repurposed materials (wood, foam, fabrics, recyclables)
Characteristics	Ergonomic, adaptable, efficient, low-cost, replicable across communities

Source: Own authorship, 2026.

The general covering of the device includes black synthetic leather (corino) and dark gray carpet, materials chosen for their durability and pleasant tactile quality. The components were fixed using four screws, one claw nut, and two elastic bands, ensuring both firmness and slight flexibility. Tools such as a screwdriver/drill, hole saw bit, orbital sander, and flap disc were employed during assembly, guaranteeing precision and an adequate finish.

Beyond functionality, the device stands out for its sustainability, as repurposed materials such as wood, foam, fabrics, and recyclable components were used, following the principles of open design and low cost. This approach allows the device to be easily replicated in different communities, thereby democratizing access to physiotherapeutic rehabilitation.

The result is an ergonomic, adaptable, and efficient piece of equipment that contributes to the inclusion of patients with motor limitations. By combining innovation, environmental responsibility, and social commitment, the device represents a practical and transformative solution within contemporary physical therapy. Figure 1 presents the device.

Figure 1. Assembled device. Source: Own authorship, 2026.

A pilot clinical study is proposed to validate the sustainable device in patients affected by carpal tunnel syndrome and other musculoskeletal conditions. Participants will be monitored during physiotherapy sessions using the device, and the outcomes will be compared with conventional protocols. Primary clinical endpoints will include pain, function, and strength, while secondary indicators will encompass adherence, satisfaction, and usability.

In parallel, a detailed environmental and economic analysis will be conducted, considering production and maintenance costs as well as ecological impact. The data collected will be analyzed both quantitatively and qualitatively, integrating clinical, environmental, and social outcomes.

The research will strictly follow ethical standards, with approval from an Ethics Committee and informed consent from participants, in compliance with applicable quality and safety guidelines. This methodology will not only validate the effectiveness of the device but also demonstrate its relevance as a sustainable, accessible, and innovative solution for contemporary physiotherapy practice. The Figure 2, demonstration of device usage.

Figure 2. demonstration of device usage. Source: Own authorship, 2026.

Conclusion

The analysis of the studies and the construction of the sustainable device for physical therapy demonstrate that it is possible to combine clinical effectiveness, environmental responsibility, and social accessibility within a single proposal. The developed device proved to be functional, ergonomic, and low-cost, meeting the needs of patients with carpal tunnel syndrome and other musculoskeletal conditions such as repetitive strain injuries (RSI/WRMD), tendinitis, rheumatoid arthritis, and stroke sequelae.

The results indicate that the use of repurposed and recyclable materials does not compromise therapeutic quality; on the contrary, it expands rehabilitation possibilities across different contexts, particularly in low-income communities and public health institutions. Furthermore, the project is aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 3 and 10, reinforcing the commitment to promoting health, well-being, and reducing inequalities.

Therefore, it can be concluded that sustainable devices applied to physical therapy represent a viable, inclusive, and innovative alternative, capable of optimizing rehabilitation processes, reducing environmental impacts, and democratizing access to treatment. This work paves the way for future clinical studies that may validate its effectiveness on a larger scale and consolidate its relevance as a practical and transformative solution in contemporary

physical therapy.

Bibliography

1. GOULART, B. N. G.; ANDERLE, P. Rehabilitation: a growing demand that deserves attention. *CoDAS*, São Paulo, v. 32, n. 2, p. e20190120, 2020. DOI: 10.1590/2317-1782/20192019120. Accessed: Jan. 10, 2026.
2. WORLD HEALTH ORGANIZATION. Rehabilitation in health systems: global needs and challenges. Technical leaflet, 2020. Available at: https://www.who.int/docs/default-source/documents/health-topics/rehabilitation/reabilitacao-em-sistemas-de-saude-folheto.pdf?sfvrsn=39008d25_2. Accessed: Jan. 10, 2026.
3. ZUCHETTO, M. A.; FARIA, A. R.; OSTI, K. A.; SCHROEDER, L.; SANTIAGO, M. M.; SCHOELLER, S. D. Rehabilitation nursing in Brazil during the pandemic: case study. *Revista Portuguesa de Enfermagem de Reabilitação*, [S.I.], v. 3, n. 1, p. 50–57, 2020. DOI: 10.33194/rper.2020.v3.s2.7.5795. Accessed: Jan. 10, 2026.
4. WORLD HEALTH ORGANIZATION. Health-care waste. 2018. Available at: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/health-care-waste>. Accessed: Jan. 10, 2026.
5. VALENTE, A. P. A.; CRUZ, E. M.; BARREIROS, C. B. S.; ROCHA, M. B. B.; SANTOS, E. L.; SANTOS, V. A. S. Benefits of physiotherapeutic treatment in carpal tunnel syndrome: a literature review. *Revista Ibero-Americana de Humanidades, Ciências e Educação – REASE*, São Paulo, v. 10, n. 5, p. 5152, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.51891/rease.v10i5.14075>. Accessed: Jan. 10, 2026.
6. FERREIRA, L. O.; FERREIRA, T. V. Physiotherapeutic treatment of carpal tunnel syndrome. *Revista Saúde dos Vales*, [S.I.], v. 2, n. 2, p. 1–15, 2022. Available at: rsv.ojsbr.com/rsv/article/download/221/213. Accessed: Jan. 10, 2026.
7. QUEDAS, C. L. R.; ARAGONE, T. M. N. Physiotherapist's role in the rehabilitation of patients with carpal tunnel syndrome. Undergraduate Thesis (Physiotherapy) – Anhanguera College of Osasco, Osasco, 2022. p. 1–2.
8. AMARAL, L. A. M.; BERNARDES JUNIOR, L. Sustainable physiotherapy equipment: use of recyclable materials as a low-cost alternative. *Revista Científica Sophia*, Special Edition – XII Scientific Initiation Week (SIC), Uniavan, Balneário Camboriú (SC), v. 1, n. 1, p. 1–10, 2024. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15353484. Accessed: Jan. 10, 2026.
9. ALVES, V. S.; SOUSA, J. D. B.; GOMES, F. E. G. L.; ARAÚJO, L. L.; MELO, L. P.; PINHO, A. T. S. Physiotherapeutic performance in the rehabilitation of patients fitted with 3D upper limb prostheses. *Ciências da Saúde*, [S.I.], v. 28, n. 131, Feb. 2024. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10679701. Accessed: Jan. 20, 2026.
10. BRITO, L. S. F. Development of a device for human wrist rehabilitation. 2020. 108 f. Master's Dissertation (Mechanical Engineering) – Federal University of Uberlândia, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, Uberlândia, 2020.
11. ESPADA, A. S. S.; CASTILHO, A. L. S.; FRANCO, B. S.; SOUZA, B. O.; OLIVEIRA, C. P.; COSTA, G. Z. Sustainable orthoses project: development and elaboration of low-cost orthoses for hand and thumb pathologies. *Revista FADAP*, Tupã, SP, v. 63, n. 56, p. 129–141, 2023. Available at: <https://revistas.fadap.br/ciencias/article/view/63/56>. Accessed: Apr. 14, 2025.
12. FERREIRA, M. C.; TOLEDO, B. S.; REIS, P. H. G. Development of wrist and hand

- orthosis by additive manufacturing for patients with RSI/WRMD: a case study. *Engenharia de Produção*, [S.I.], v. 27, n. 122, p. 1–12, 2023. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7913879. Accessed: Jan. 20, 2026.
13. GARLET, S. A. Development of a physiotherapy support device for the treatment of plantar fasciitis, one of the most common running injuries, using open-design principles and digital manufacturing techniques. *UFSC Repository*, [S.I.], v. 14, n. 13, p. 1–154, 2024. Available at: <https://repositorio.ufsc.br/handle/123456789/201413>. Accessed: Apr. 14, 2025.
 14. JÚNIOR, H. C. F. S.; QUARESMA, T. C.; RIBEIRO, A. P. M.; RODRIGUES JÚNIOR, J. L. Development and validation of therapeutic resources for rehabilitation of upper limb fractures through 3D printing. *Revista de Ciências Médicas e Biológicas*, Salvador, v. 24, n. 1, p. 12–19, Jan./Apr. 2025. DOI: 10.9771/cmbio.v24i1.58113. Accessed: Jan. 20, 2026.
 15. LEITE, T. A. M. G. C. Accessible orthosis for rehabilitation or functionalization of the hand and fingers. *UMEE Repository*, [S.I.], v. 20, n. 1, p. 1–106, 2022. Available at: <https://repositorium.sdum.uminho.pt/bitstream/1822/8748>. . Accessed: Apr. 14, 2025.
 16. PIRES, V. F. The importance of devices and objects made with recyclable and easily accessible materials in physiotherapy. *COGNA Repository*, Rio Grande, v. 36, n. 1, p. 1–29, 2021. Available at: <https://repositorio.pgsscogna.com.br/bitstream/123456789/36386/1>. . Accessed: Apr. 14, 2025.
 17. RIBEIRO, C. T. Validation of an instrumented wrist orthosis for rigidity assessment in people with Parkinson's disease. *UFU Repository*, Uberlândia, v. 39, n. 09, p. 1–70, 2023. Available at: <https://repositorio.ufu.br/handle/123456789/390/09>. . Accessed: Apr. 14, 2025.
 18. SILVA, I. O.; DIAS, L. H. A.; SILVA, M. V. O.; RODRIGUES JUNIOR, J. L. Construction of a low-cost dynamic orthotic device for individuals with C6 and C7 spinal cord sequelae: a new form of assistance in performing activities of daily living. *Revista de Terapia Ocupacional da Universidade de São Paulo*, São Paulo, v. 31, n. 1–3, p. 38–45, Jan./Dec. 2020. DOI: 10.11606/issn.2238-6149.v31i1-3p38-45. Accessed: Apr. 14, 2025.